

Roman Divination

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Entry tags: Religion, Hellenistic Religions, Greek Religions, Roman Religious Traditions, Roman State Religions, Greek Religions in Rome, Italic Religions

Augury refers narrowly to officially-sanctioned divination via the flights of birds. More broadly, it can refer to divination of a variety of natural sorts, ranging from weather phenomena, to different animals, to other signs. Such divination was not predictive of future events, but rather evaluative about the gods' will. Augurs were official, elite positions in the Roman world. However, there is evidence for non-official, non-elite (but still specialized) augurs long before Roman times (Egypt, Etruscan, Greek) as well as during the height of the Empire.

Date Range: 800 BCE - 380 CE

Region: Roman Empire

Region tags: Europe, Southeastern Europe, Southern Europe, Middle East

Greek, Etruscan, Roman, like others (Egypt, Cyprus, etc.)

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Cicero, "On Divination", "On the Nature of the Gods", "On the Laws"
- Source 2: Titus Livius (Livy), "On the History of Rome (Ab Urbe Condita)"
- Source 3: Pliny the Elder, "Natural History"

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: http://penelope.uchicago.edu/Thayer/e/roman/texts/secondary/smigra*/augurium.html
- Source 1 Description: William Smith, "A Dictionary of Greek and Roman Antiquities" (London: John Murray, 1875)
- Source 2 URL: http://www.societasviaromana.net/Collegium_Religionis/augury.php
- Source 2 Description: Societas Via Romana
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.britannica.com/topic/augury>
- Source 3 Description: Encyclopedia Britannica

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: http://penelope.uchicago.edu/Thayer/E/Roman/Texts/Cicero/de_Divinatione/2*.html

- Source 1 Description: Cicero, "On Divination"
- Source 2 URL: <http://mcadams.posc.mu.edu/txt/ah/Livy/>
- Source 2 Description: Livy, "On the History of Rome"
- Source 3 URL: <http://www.perseus.tufts.edu/hopper/text?doc=Plin.+Nat.+toc>
- Source 3 Description: Pliny the Elder, "Natural History"

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by class:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

↳ Assigned by gender:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– Yes [specify]: Specialized training

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– Yes

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– Yes

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– Yes

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– Yes

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– Yes

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– Yes

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– Field doesn't know

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– Yes

↳ Apostates are socially shunned and/or publicly vilified:

– Yes

↳ Wealth, civil rights, and/or social capital are taken by authorities:

– Yes

↳ Do apostates receive corporal punishment:

– Yes

↳ Do apostates receive divine punishment:

– Yes

↳ Punished in the afterlife:

– No

↳ Cursed by "high god":

– Field doesn't know

↳ Cursed by other supernatural being(s):

– Yes

↳ Other divine punishment:

– Yes [specify]: General misfortune stemming from nature, e.g. natural disasters, disease

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Official Roman augurs numbered four (4) and then nine (9); other augurs across empire varied widely by time, region

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 99

Notes: Nearly entire population in Roman Empire adhered to differing degrees to polytheistic structure and related divinatory practices

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (trying to be organized-controlled by larger religious group)

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– No

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– No

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– No

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Yes

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– No

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:

– No

↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:

– Yes

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:

– Yes

↳ A political leader chooses the leader:

– Yes

↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:

– Yes

↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:

– No

↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:

– No

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– Yes

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: No official "scriptures", but the augurs would take notes and refer to past such books that were considered somewhat holy

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: Present in Roman religion, but not around the augurs themselves

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– No

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

↳ Are sacred site oriented to ecological features:

– Yes

Notes: Cardinal directions, as well as the direction of various notable urban points in Rome

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– No

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– Yes [specify]: Body was considered to persist in some diminished form after death in the underworld

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

↳ Cremation:

– Yes

↳ Mummification:

– No

↳ Interment:

– Yes

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– No

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Yes

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– No

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

Notes: Rarely; possible with heroic individuals

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– Yes [specify]: High status individuals would have a large feast and monument erected

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Field doesn't know

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

↳ Valuable items:

– Yes

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– Yes

Notes: Depending on status of individual

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Yes

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:

– Yes [specify]: Weapons, priestly effects

↳ Other grave goods:

– Yes

Notes: Vestments especially holy items

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– Yes

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– Yes [specify]: Some monumental structures

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– Yes

Notes: More so heroes than elites

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– Yes [specify]: Patron of cities

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– No

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: Olympian deities themselves overthrew previous "high deities"

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

Notes: Jupiter sometimes knows; at other times does not

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Jupiter can seemingly not see everywhere at once; he pays more attention to notable places

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: In theory there are no specific restrictions

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Jupiter presumably can influence areas outside of Roman Empire's boundaries

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– No

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: Can predict future, but not perfectly

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– Yes

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: Shape-shifting; amorous desires

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: Divinatory practices around animals, natural world, other portents

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Heroes or human spirits often tied to particular places

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: In theory, spirits can move a variety of places

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Notes: In theory, heroes / spirits can influence affairs outside of Roman Empire

- ↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Yes
 - Notes: Potentially, but not necessarily
- ↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes
 - Notes: Potentially, but not necessarily
- ↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:
 - Yes [specify]: Events past especially
- ↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits can reward:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits can punish:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits have memory of life:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination processes:

– Yes

↳ Only through specialists:

– Yes

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Communicate with living through other means:

– Yes [specify]: Natural portents

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:
– Yes [specify]: Past events especially

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
– Yes [specify]: Some can shape-shift; others tied to particular geographic features

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:
– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be seen:
– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can reward:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can punish:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess hunger:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: Often tied to particular geographic feature

↳ Mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: In Underworld; at particular geographic locations

↳ Does the religious group possess a pantheon of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– Yes

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

Notes: Mostly; crossover is possible

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– Yes [specify]: Also highly diffuse at certain times; non-systematic understanding of pantheon

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

↳ Food:

– No

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: They can compete with or help one another

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

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↳ Adultery:

– Yes

↳ Incest:

– Yes

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: Animalphilia

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: Compete or aid one another

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: Cause is usually but not always known; it is frequently inferred

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Other, lesser entities can do the will of higher gods

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– No

↳ Done randomly:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Can be done as part of proxy war against other gods or groups

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Underworld is for all people; some believe that there is a sort of paradise after death (Elysium Fields); matter of debate

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Direct harm or death possible, especially via nature

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

- ↳ Done only by high god:
 - No
- ↳ Done by many supernatural beings:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to enforce group norms:
 - No
- ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
 - No
- ↳ Done randomly:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:
 - Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:
– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:
– Yes

↳ Other [specify]
– Yes

Notes: See note on punishments after death; Elysium Fields are subject to debate as to breadth of belief

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
– No

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - Yes

Notes: Material wealth; enhanced beauty; long life; worshipped after death as hero; etc.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

- ↳ What is the nature of this distinction:
 - Present (but not emphasized)

- ↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:
 - Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:
– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:
– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):
– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:
– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:
– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:
– Yes

↳ Moral norms apply to:
– Only specialized religious class
– Only one class of society
– Only one gender
– All individuals within society (excepting slaves, aliens)
– All individuals within society

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:
– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):
– Yes

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– No

↳ Generosity / charity:

– No

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– No

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Yes

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

↳ Cooperation:

– No

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– No

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Yes

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– Yes

↳ Strength (physical):

– Yes

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– Yes

↳ Humility / modesty:

– No

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– No

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:

– Yes

↳ Optimism / hope:

– Yes

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– Yes

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– Yes

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– Yes

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– Yes

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– Yes

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– Yes

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes [specify]: Militarism

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Number of participants: 100

Notes: This can and did vary widely

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– No

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– No

↳ Circumcision:

– No

↳ Food taboos:

– No

↳ Hair:

– No

↳ Dress:

– Yes

↳ Ornaments:

– Yes

↳ Archaic ritual language:

– Yes

↳ Other:

– Field doesn't know

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

- An empire
- A state
- Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Augurs were a specific class of diviners, within the broader society

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

- No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

- Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

- No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

- Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

- No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

- Field doesn't know

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

- Yes

↳ Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

- No

↳ Is such education open to both males and females:

- No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Fishing

– Pastoralism

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Rome received tithes in the form of food (often grain) from its subject states